

Dyes derived from Oxalyldibenzylketone.

Part I.

Azine and Azonium Derivatives.

By

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Dibenzylketone condenses with oxalic ester in presence of sodium ethoxide (Claisen and Ewan, *Annalen*, 1885, 284, 250) yielding oxalyldibenzylketone which may be otherwise called 2:4:5-triketo-1:3-diphenyl-R-pentamethylene. This substance is an α -diketone and may be expected to condense with *o*-diamines to form azines. Claisen and Ewan (*loc. cit.*) condensed it with *o*-tolylenediamine. The present author has condensed it also with *o*-phenylenediamine, 1:2-naphthylene diamine and brom- and chlor-tolylenediamines in order to compare the colour of these azines with that of the phenanthrazines and acenaphthazines.

It has been found that the products nearly resemble the phenanthrazines and acenaphthazines in colour and dyeing properties.

It will be observed that both phenanthraquinone and acenaphthaquinone contain three nuclei which are fused together. But in oxalyldibenzylketone two phenyl residues are only linked with a pentamethylene ring. As the presence of condensed ring systems acts "bathochromically," that is, tends to increase the intensity of colour in compounds, it might be reasonably supposed that phenanthraphenazine and acenaphthaphenazine would be more strongly coloured than the azine from oxalyldibenzylketone. But since that is not the case, it is evident that the presence of the additional

chromophere, *viz.*, the CO group in the molecule greatly intensifies the colour in the latter type of compounds. Most of the azines described above are bright yellow substances which show characteristic colour reactions with concentrated sulphuric acid and dye unmordanted wool in uniform and fine shades from a neutral bath.

It was supposed that the dyeing properties of these dyestuffs would be greatly augmented if these compounds could be made soluble in water. With this object in view oxalyldibenzylketone was condensed with *o*-phenylenediamine sulphonic acid, 1:2-naphthylenediamine sulphonic acid and diamionaphthol sulphonic acids. But the products so obtained, although somewhat soluble in water, were found to possess no superior dyeing properties.

It has been observed that in the azine series the tinctorial properties of a compound are greatly enhanced by the conversion of a nitrogen atom from the tervalent to the quinquevalent state, that is, by changing an *azine* to an *azonium* compound. With this object in view oxalyldibenzylketone was condensed with 1-amino-2-phenylamino-naphthalene in the presence of hydrochloric and nitric acids. The chloride so obtained has a brown colour while the nitrate is scarlet red. But contrary to expectation these compounds have not very marked dyeing properties. The nitrate may be represented by the following diagram :

A further study of the azonium compounds as well as the glyoxalines derived from oxalyldibenzylketone is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Product from orthoPhenylenediamine and Oxalyldibenzylketone.—2.6 gms. of oxalyldibenzylketone are mixed with 1.1 gm. of *o*-phenylenediamine and 50 c. c. of absolute alcohol. The mixture is boiled under reflux for 3 to 4 hours. The precipitate obtained on cooling is crystallised from acetone. It is a bright pink crystalline substance melting at 251°. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a deep pink colour which turns brown on dilution. The freshly-precipitated substance dyes yellow shades on unmordanted wool from neutral bath.

(Found : C=82.31; H=4.65; N=7.80. $C_{16}H_{16}N_2O$ requires C=82.14; H=4.76 and N=8.33 per cent.)

Product from 1:3:4-orthoTolylenediamine and Oxalyldibenzylketone.—The precipitate obtained by boiling an absolute alcoholic solution of 5.2 gms. of oxalyldibenzylketone and 2.5 gms. of *o*-tolylenediamine for 4-5 hours is crystallised from a yellow mixture of pyridine and water. The prismatic crystals melt at 285° and dissolve in concentrated sulphuric acid with a pink solution. The compound dyes brown shades on wool.

(Found : N=7.89. $C_{24}H_{18}N_2O$ requires N=8.00 per cent.). (Cf. Claisen and Ewan, *loc. cit.*)

Product from 1:3:4:5-Bromtolylenediamine and Oxalyldibenzylketone.—The compound is obtained similarly by heating equimolecular quantities of the diamine and the ketone in alcoholic solution and crystallising it from a mixture of pyridine and water. The crystals are

ochre-coloured prisms melting above 300° . They dissolve in concentrated sulphuric acid with a deep red colour and dye wool in pink shades.

(Found: Br=18.10. $C_{24}H_{17}BrN_2O$ requires Br=18.41 per cent.).

Product from 1 : 2-Naphthylenediamine and Oxalyldibenzylketone.—It is obtained as the previous compound and crystallised from xylene. The crystals are deep yellow prisms melting at 288° and dissolving in conc. sulphuric acid with a violet solution. They dye wool in gamboge shades.

(Found: N=7.51. $C_{27}H_{18}N_2O$ requires N=7.25 per cent.).

Product from 1:2:3-orthoPhenylenediamine sulphonic Acid and Oxalyldibenzylketone.—Equimolecular quantities of the ketone and the sulphonic acid are boiled with a little water for 5-6 hours. The precipitate is extracted with a large quantity of water which on cooling deposits yellow crystals of the azinesulphonic acid.

(Found: N=6.54. $C_{25}H_{18}N_2O_4S$ requires N=6.73 per cent.).

Product from 1 : 2-Diamino-8-naphthol-6-sulphonic Acid and Oxalyldibenzylketone.—The product is obtained in the same way as the previous one and the precipitate purified through the calcium salt. It is sparingly soluble in hot water.

(Found: N=5.75. $C_{27}H_{18}N_2O_5S$ requires N=5.81 per cent.).

Product from 1 : 2 : 4-Naphthylenediamine Sulphonic Acid and Oxalyldibenzylketone.—Equivalent quantities

of the sulphonic acid and the ketone are boiled with a small quantity of water and the product purified through the calcium compound as above. It is obtained as a yellow amorphous precipitate.

(Found: N=5.93. $C_{27}H_{18}N_2O_4S$ requires N=6.01 per cent..)

Product from 1:6:3:4-Chlortolylenediamine and Oxalyldibenzylketone—2.5 gms. of oxalyldibenzylketone and 1.3 gms. of the diamine are boiled in absolute alcoholic solution for 5-6 hours. The crystalline precipitate is recrystallised from a mixture of pyridine and water and melts above 300°.

(Found: N=7.14. $C_{34}H_{17}ClN_2O$ requires N=7.28 per cent.)

Product from 1-Amino-2-phenylamino-naphthalene and Oxalyldibenzylketone.—The amine and the ketone are dissolved in equimolecular quantities in glacial acetic acid and a few c.c.s of conc. hydrochloric acid are added to the mixture and warmed. A precipitate of the hydrochloride is at once formed, and is crystallised from alcohol in brown crystals, m. p. 195°.

(Found: N=5.62. $C_9H_9N_2OCl$ requires N=5.75 per cent.)

The *nitrate* is obtained like the chloride by using concentrated nitric acid in the above reaction instead of hydrochloric acid. The dark red solution on treatment with one or two drops of water gives a scarlet red crystalline precipitate of the nitrate which is washed with alcohol and ether. This is recrystallised from absolute alcohol and melts above 300°. It gives a dark brown

solution in conc. sulphuric acid and dyes unmordanted wool in light brown shades.

(Found: N=8.23. $C_{32}H_2N_3O_4$ requires N=8.18 per cent.).

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